

Grant Agreement number: 101132559

Project acronym: ST4TE

Project title: Strategies for just and equitable transitions in Europe

Type of action: RIA

Case Study

'Structural problems of the labour market with a prospective analysis of future challenges intersecting migration and youth issues'

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Due date	08 May 2026
Actual submission date	05 May 2026
Dissemination Level	Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101132559.

Document Revision History

Date	Version	Author/Editor/Contributor	Summary of main changes / Status
02/10/25	0.1	Goulaptsi Maria, Kakderi Christina	Structure and background analysis
01/12/25	0.2	Goulaptsi Maria, Kakderi Christina	Stakeholders mapping
03/01/26	0.3	Goulaptsi Maria, Kakderi Christina	Policy analysis
09/02/26	0.4	Goulaptsi Maria, Kakderi Christina	Assumptions and drivers
25/03/26	0.5	Goulaptsi Maria, Kakderi Christina	Final remarks
29/04/26	0.6	Matias Barberis (EFIS Centre)	Quality review
04/05/26	1.0	Goulaptsi Maria, Kakderi Christina	Minor edits, final version

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Executive summary

The Netherlands is one of Europe's strongest digital performers, supported by world-class connectivity, a robust research and innovation base, and globally competitive high-tech sectors. It consistently ranks among the top EU Member States on DESI and already exceeds the EU's 2030 target for basic digital skills, with 82.7% of the population demonstrating at least basic proficiency. Broadband and 5G coverage are near universal, and Dutch enterprises show strong uptake of core digital technologies.

Beneath this strong performance, however, lie structural vulnerabilities that increasingly shape the country's digital transition. Persistent shortages of ICT and technical professionals, a limited pipeline of ICT graduates, demographic ageing, and recent restrictions on foreign labour constrain the pace of digitalisation. Labour market tightness is particularly acute in digital and engineering occupations, and the number of ICT graduates remains insufficient to meet projected demand.

Digital inequalities also persist across social groups, regions, and sectors. Migrants, low-literate adults, and older people face barriers to digital participation, while gender imbalance remains structural, with women representing only a small share of ICT specialists. SMEs lag behind larger firms in adopting advanced technologies such as AI and data analytics, reflecting resource constraints and fragmented regional innovation ecosystems.

The Dutch response centers on the **Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs**, which aims to strengthen the talent pipeline, improve labour market functioning, accelerate productivity-enhancing innovation, and reduce governance fragmentation. Embedded within the revised **Digital Decade National Roadmap**, the plan is supported by €5.25 billion across 59 measures, complemented by STEM reforms, the Master Plan for Basic Skills, and EU-funded initiatives through the RRP, ESF+, and ERDF.

This case study examines how structural labour shortages, demographic trends, and uneven access to digital opportunities shape the inclusiveness of the Dutch digital transition, illustrating how strong national performance can coexist with persistent inequalities that limit both the pace and equity of digital transformation.

1 Introduction

The Netherlands occupies a historically significant position in the development of the global digital economy. On **17 November 1988**, the Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica (CWI) in Amsterdam established Europe's first connection to the public internet and registered the **.nl domain** — the **first country-code domain in Europe**. This early positioning reflected the country's longstanding strengths in logistics, trade, and telecommunications infrastructure, and laid the foundation for what would become one of the world's most advanced digital economies. During the 1990s, the Dutch digital landscape underwent rapid transformation. In January 1994, the internet became available to the public via De Digitale Stad — the Digital City — a pioneering public access initiative. The Amsterdam Internet Exchange (AMS-IX), established in 1997, further consolidated the Netherlands' position as a central node of European digital infrastructure.

The **first formal national digitalisation strategy was introduced in 2018**, marking a shift from infrastructure-led growth to a more coordinated policy approach covering privacy, cybersecurity, digital literacy, and fair competition. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the Netherlands allocated 26% of its Recovery and Resilience Plan — approximately €1.2 billion — to digital priorities, including investments in quantum technology, artificial intelligence, the digitalisation of education, and smart mobility infrastructure. These successive investments have cumulatively reinforced the Netherlands' position as one of Europe's leading digital economies.

Today, the country ranks among the **top performers in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)**, supported by a strong research ecosystem, advanced connectivity infrastructure, and globally competitive high-tech industries. **Near-universal Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) coverage, strong enterprise digitalisation, and the highest share of citizens with at least basic digital skills in the EU** reflect the accumulated outcomes of decades of sustained public and private investment in digital infrastructure and skills.

According to the Netherlands 2025 Digital Decade Country Report, 82.7% of the Dutch population possesses basic digital skills, already surpassing the EU's 2030 target.

Table 1 Digital Decade KPI

Digital Decade KPI (1)	The Netherlands				EU		Digital Decade target by 2030	
	DESI 2024 (year 2023)	DESI 2025* (year 2024)	Annual progress	National trajectory 2024 (3)	DESI 2025	Annual progress	NL	EU
Fixed Very High-Capacity Network (VHCN) coverage	98.3%	98.4%	0.1%	97.8%	82.5%	4.9%	100.0%	100%
Fibre-to-the-Premises (FTTP) coverage	77.7%	85.3%	9.9%	-	69.2%	8.4%	-	-
Overall 5G coverage	100.0%	100.0%	0.0%	100.0%	94.3%	5.9%	100.0%	100%
Edge Nodes (estimate)	27	59	118.5%	-	2 257	90.5%	-	10000
SMEs with at least a basic level of digital intensity	-	80.8%	0.5%	-	72.9%	2.8%	95.0%	90%
Cloud	60.4%	68.5%	13.5%	-	-	-	85.3%	75%
Artificial Intelligence	14.1%	23.1%	63.5%	23.0%	13.5%	67.2%	85.1%	75%

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Digital Decade KPI (1)	The Netherlands				EU		Digital Decade target by 2030	
	DESI 2024 (year 2023)	DESI 2025* (year 2024)	Annual progress	National trajectory 2024 (3)	DESI 2025	Annual progress	NL	EU
Data analytics	50.8%	-	-	-	-	-	75.0%	75%
AI or Cloud or Data analytics	74.6%	-	-	-	-	-	-	75%
Unicorns	30	32	6.7%	-	286	4.4%	-	500
At least basic digital skills	82.7%	-	-	-	-	-	100.0%	80%
ICT specialists	6.9%	7.0%	1.4%	7.7%	5.0%	4.2%	9.2%	~10%
eID scheme notification		Yes						
Digital public services for citizens	85.9	88.5	3.1%	85.9	82.3	3.6%	100.0	100
Digital public services for businesses	86.7	88.8	2.4%	86.7	86.2	0.9%	100.0	100
Access to e-health records	72.5	65.2	-10.1%	-	82.7	4.5%	-	100

*DESI 2025 reports the version 4 of the Digital Intensity Index, that is comparable with the DII value from DESI 2023 (referring to year 2022) for the calculation of the annual progress.

Source: European Commission “the Netherlands 2025 Digital Decade Country Report”

According to the special Eurobarometer on ‘the Digital Decade 2025’, 84% of the Dutch public consider that **“the digitalisation of daily public and private services is making their lives easier”**. Regarding competitiveness, 83% deem it significant that European companies can grow and become “European Champions” able to compete globally. However, this strong performance masks several structural challenges. The Dutch labour market faces persistent shortages in ICT and technical professions, driven by demographic ageing, limited ICT graduate output, and recent restrictions on foreign labour.

As the Digital Decade Country Report 2025 report notes, **“ICT graduates are a small number to be able to fill the job gaps”**. Moreover, ICT specialists represented 7% of the Netherlands’ total workforce (the 2030 national target is 9.2%), which is higher than the EU average of 5%, however, the country is lagging behind its national trajectory. **With ICT specialists representing 6.9% of the total workforce in 2023, the growth rate observed in the Netherlands is much lower than the EU average (+4.2%)**. Even though, Netherlands is ranked 3rd among the EU member states for the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) and there are 673.7 thousand ICT specialists based on 2023 data, ICT graduates are only 4.40% of graduates based on 2022 data.

Dutch digital transition policy is embedded in a multilayered framework that integrates national strategies with EU-level instruments, with the **Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs** playing a central role in addressing acute labour shortages in ICT, engineering, and technical professions through reskilling, upskilling, and structured partnerships across employers, education providers, and public authorities. This labour-market focus aligns closely with the broader ambitions set out in the **Digital Decade National Roadmap**, which connects Dutch priorities to the EU’s 2030 objectives.

The Netherlands 2025 Digital Decade Country Report includes a fully revised **national Digital Decade roadmap**. The revised Netherlands’ roadmap is composed of 59 measures with a budget of EUR 5.25 billion, of which EUR 5.22 billion comes from public budgets, equivalent to 0.46% of GDP.

The measures cluster around four broad areas: **a. Connectivity and infrastructure** — connectivity infrastructure is described as in good shape, with high broadband coverage and

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excellent 5G services, and the roadmap includes measures to **maintain and extend this lead**, including on fibre rollout and 5G standalone networks, **b. Digital skills and ICT workforce** — the roadmap has been adjusted to support ICT teaching and regional plans to increase the ICT workforce, including measures **targeting untapped talent pools such as people with a migrant background and part-time workers**, and addressing the gender imbalance in digital occupations, **c. Business digitalisation** — smaller Dutch enterprises often lag in adopting key digital technologies, especially AI, partly due to the fragmented, regionally driven nature of AI innovation, and **measures target SME uptake of cloud, data analytics and AI** and **d. Sustainable digitalisation and public services** — the Netherlands is stepping up its commitment to sustainable digitalisation with the launch of the Sustainable Digitalisation Action Plan alongside continued investment in digital public services and online safety.

Complementary education and skills reforms, including the **Master Plan for Basic Skills**, strengthened STEM pathways, and efforts to embed digital literacy in schools, seek to mitigate persistent ICT talent shortages. EU funding instruments provide essential support for digital skills, innovation, and infrastructure: the Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP) contributes approximately €1.2 billion (26% of the Dutch RRP) for digital priorities including AI and quantum technology; the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) allocates approximately €522 million for labour market integration and reskilling under the 2021–2027 programming period; the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) supports regional digital infrastructure and SME digitalisation; and the Digital Europe Programme co-funds the six national European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) at €1.8 million per hub per year.

This case study aims to analyse the inequality drivers of the digital transition policy in the Netherlands, by examining the national initiatives directed towards addressing structural workforce shortages in ICT and technical professions. Yet as the following sections demonstrate, this strong aggregate performance masks persistent structural vulnerabilities — in workforce supply, in social inclusion, and in the equitable distribution of digital opportunities — that define the policy challenge the Netherlands now faces. The focus of the analysis will be on the **Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs**. The Dutch case is selected because it illustrates the tensions that can exist between strong aggregate digital performance and persistent structural inequalities.

2 The digital transition policy process

The Netherlands approaches the digital transition from a position of considerable strength, consistently outperforming the EU average across most Digital Decade indicators. As already highlighted, persistent ICT labour shortages, demographic ageing, uneven institutional capacity, and slower uptake of advanced technologies such as AI and data analytics reveal structural vulnerabilities that require a more coordinated and forward-looking policy response.

2.1 The Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs: A Structural Response to Workforce Constraints in the Digital Transition- Policy design

The **Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs** adopted in 2023 and covering the period 2023–2033, represents the Dutch government’s most comprehensive attempt to date to address the structural workforce challenges that threaten to constrain the country’s digital transition. The **Action Plan** was jointly formulated by the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy (EZK), the Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment (SZW), and the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (OCW). This policy is anchored in a cross-ministerial analytical assessment that identifies persistent workforce shortages as a structural impediment to the digital transformation of the Dutch economy. This diagnostic framing is institutionally significant: rather than interpreting labour shortages as sector-specific frictions, the Action Plan conceptualises them as systemic constraints that fundamentally condition the feasibility, sequencing and overall tempo of the Netherlands’ broader transition agenda.

Figure 1 Structure of APDB; Source: Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs (2023) and Monitor AGDB (2025)

The policy architecture of the **Action Plan** is organised around **four pillars**, each one addressing a distinct mechanism within the skills and productivity system. The **first pillar** focuses on **strengthening the educational pipeline** by enhancing the visibility, quality and attractiveness of technical and technological learning pathways. The underlying diagnosis is that insufficient early exposure to technology contributes to under-informed study choices, elevated dropout rates and leakage of graduates from technical fields. To address these issues, the government has committed substantial structural investments, over the ten-year period to 2033, including **€150 million for science and technology education sector plans, €100 million for practice-oriented research linking education and industry, €14 million to support lateral entry and reduce attrition in higher vocational education (HBO), and €33 million to reinforce career guidance in secondary vocational education (MBO).**

These financial commitments are complemented by a broader set of systemic measures aimed at **strengthening cooperation between education providers and employers**, improving curricular alignment with labour-market needs, expanding hybrid learning environments and dual learning pathways, and enhancing early exposure to technology across primary and secondary education. Additional actions include reinforcing study guidance and labour-market information systems, implementing targeted interventions to reduce dropout in technical programmes, facilitating lateral entry into technical fields, and examining the potential role of mandatory social service as an additional recruitment channel into shortage sectors. Collectively, **these measures seek to establish a more coherent, responsive and future-oriented talent pipeline capable of supporting the Netherlands' digital transition.**

The **second pillar** targets labour-market functioning, recognising that increasing educational inflow is insufficient without improving retention, mobility, and working conditions for technical and ICT professionals. Policy measures include subsidies to stimulate lateral inflow from adjacent occupations, **enhanced matching through expanded public employment services and regional public-private ICT partnerships**, and a suite of lifelong-learning initiatives—such as “Strong with Skills”, “Learning Overview platform” and the National Lifelong Learning Catalyst—designed to **promote a skills-based rather than credentials-based labour market.** The plan also incorporates targeted interventions to increase participation from under-represented groups, including through the VIA (Further Integration in the Labour Market programme), the Coalition Women in Tech, and the IT Taskforce, while scaling up successful vocational pathways in VET to strengthen structured entry routes into technical and ICT professions. The **third pillar** addresses a structural dimension of the workforce challenge: the recognition that labour shortages cannot be resolved solely through supply-side expansion. Given demographic trends and the scale of transition-related labour demand, productivity gains within technical professions are essential. Accordingly, this pillar focuses on **accelerating technological and process innovation in firms** to reduce labour intensity and enable higher output with existing workforce capacity. Key initiatives include the “**Accelerating Digitalisation for SMEs**” supporting SME digital adoption, the “**Smart Industry programme promoting**” advanced manufacturing and industrial digitalisation, the “**My Digital Business**” initiative targeting digital transition in the retail sector, and the establishment of EDIHs providing regional access to technology testing, expertise, and investment facilitation. **The Netherlands has**

established six EDIHs — five focused on Smart Industry applications anchored in an existing regional Smart Industry Hub and one dedicated to the public sector — each operational since late 2022 or early 2023 as part of the EU's Digital Europe Programme. The hubs function as one-stop shops, offering SMEs and public sector organisations access to technical expertise, testing facilities, financing advice, and skills development support — operating on the principle of "test before invest". Financially, each hub is co-funded for seven years by the EU (40%), the national government (40%) and the regional authority (20%), at a budget of €1.8 million per year. The **five hubs** are coordinated nationally through a shared back office and a common Smart Industry programme, with specialisation distributed across the network to avoid duplication and create complementarity.

Figure 2 Dutch European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs); Source: European Commission announcement (2023)

The **fourth pillar** extends this systemic logic to the governance domain. The Dutch landscape for technical workforce development is characterised by a dense constellation of initiatives, platforms, sectoral funds, and regional partnerships—many of which perform effectively in isolation but lack sufficient coordination at the system level. Pillar 4 seeks to address this fragmentation by **establishing a simplified and transparent implementation structure** that builds on existing national and regional infrastructures, aligns the agendas of different administrative bodies, and maintains regional cooperation as the core delivery mechanism. **The analytical foundation for this governance design is provided by a dedicated Governance Report published in December 2023**, which outlines role allocation, monitoring mechanisms, and inter-ministerial coordination protocols. The resulting governance model is one of

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network governance—coordination without formal hierarchical authority—relying on the sustained commitment and mutual accountability of participating actors.

Taken together, the four pillars of the Action Plan constitute an integrated policy framework that reflects the interconnected nature of **skills development, labour-market functioning, technological innovation and governance arrangements**. The plan’s design links measures aimed at increasing educational inflow, supporting workforce mobility, enhancing firm-level productivity and improving inter-ministerial coordination, recognising that the digital transition involves multiple interdependent policy domains.

2.1.1 Stakeholders mapping

The Dutch digital transition is characterised by a dense and diverse stakeholder ecosystem spanning public authorities, public-private coalitions, and private sector actors. The table below summarises the main stakeholders and their roles.

Table 2 Action Plan for Green and Digital and Dutch digital Transition stakeholders and roles

Sector	Stakeholders	Role
Public Sector	European Commission	Provides funding, guidance, and monitoring through the Digital Decade framework.
	Ministry of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment	Lead the Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs and coordinate national digitalisation efforts.
	Association of Netherlands Municipalities (VNG)	Develops the Digital Agenda for Municipalities 2024 and supports local digitalisation.
	Association of the Provinces of the Netherlands	Coordinates regional implementation of EU programmes.
	Municipality of Amsterdam	Implements the MBO Agenda to strengthen school-to-work transitions and address local skills gaps.
Public-Private Organisation	National Coalition for Sustainable Digitalisation (NCDD)	Focuses on sustainable digitalisation, including energy-efficient data centres and green IT.
	Netherlands AI Coalition (NL AIC)	Supports AI talent development, ELSA labs, and business adoption of AI.
Private Sector	Big Tech & ICT Companies	Develop and expand digital infrastructure and advanced technologies.
	Consulting & Digital Transformation Firms	Support organisations in AI governance, cloud migration, cybersecurity, and automation.
	Startups & Innovation Ecosystem	Drive innovation, particularly in AI, fintech, and deep tech.
Citizen associations and	Digital Society Alliance	A national network that fights digital exclusion.

Sector	Stakeholders	Role
civil society groups		Works with municipalities, libraries, telecom companies, and NGOs.
	Reading & Writing Foundation	Focuses on basic literacy but increasingly addresses digital literacy for low-literacy adults.
Educational Sector	University of Amsterdam	UvA's efforts in AI research, ethical governance, and talent development, stimulating digital innovation and growing the number of digital professionals
	Maastricht University	Its contributions span education (digital and open), research (AI, IoT, innovation), policy (responsible AI), infrastructure (cloud systems), and public-good domains (open science, digital heritage).

2.2. Policy implementation

The **resulting governance model** is relying on the sustained commitment and **mutual accountability** of participating actors. Governance reforms introduced within the **Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs** further operationalise this model by establishing structured mechanisms for alignment across the “**triple helix**” partners of government, education, and industry. Strategic coordination is anchored in a newly established **Steering Council**, which provides system-level direction and ensures coherence across the four thematic pillars. Complementing this, implementation is organised through **dedicated triple-helix Core Groups for each pillar**, enabling targeted coordination at the level of specific objectives.

The **Steering Council** is chaired by a nationally appointed figurehead and supported by a government-designated secretary, while each Core Group is led by an appointed network manager. Both bodies convene at least three times per year, with network managers retaining discretion to organise additional meetings, when necessary, provided that the proliferation of new consultation structures is avoided. The governance framework deliberately limits the number of fixed stakeholders involved, thereby preserving flexibility and strengthening the capacity of network managers to provide effective strategic direction. These arrangements, grounded in the analytical foundations of the 2023 Governance Report, aim to overcome fragmentation in the Dutch technical-skills ecosystem by creating a coherent, transparent, and collaborative governance structure capable of steering the Action Plan's implementation at both national and regional levels.

Building on this network-based architecture, the **Action Plan** also incorporates mechanisms for national-level steering of budgets, policy direction, and regulatory alignment. Although the Action Plan itself does not possess formal hierarchical authority, strategic oversight is exercised through **Director-General (DG)** consultations involving the three responsible ministries. These biannual DG-level meetings serve as the highest administrative forum for resolving bottlenecks, coordinating regulatory action, and ensuring that ministerial priorities

remain aligned with the objectives of the Action Plan. Sectoral branches contribute to this process through the development and implementation of targeted action plans, reinforcing the multi-actor character of the governance model.

The connection between national steering structures and regional implementation is further strengthened through dedicated support mechanisms. The **Platform Talent for Technology (PTvT)** plays a central role by appointing a provincial account manager in each province to facilitate coordination and ensure that regional networks operate within a coherent national policy framework. In collaboration with the national secretary, PTvT also organises an inter-regional coordination forum designed to enhance alignment between national authorities and regional partnerships. Moreover, a new coordinating body launched in 2025, the **National course consultation** bringing together representatives from the education sector, the Assault Plan Technology, the Assault Plan Chronic ICT Shortage and the three lead ministries. This body meets at least three times per year to review objectives and align implementation. In 2024, all Dutch provinces, developed Regional Action Plans setting out their specific shortages, future demand for digital professionals, and planned responses.

The implementation of the Action Plan is underpinned by a combination of national and EU funding instruments that provide the financial backbone for translating governance commitments into concrete measures. At the EU level, the **European Social Fund Plus (ESF+)** provides approximately **€522 million** under the 2021–2027 programming period, channelled primarily into labour market integration, reskilling, and active inclusion measures — including the VIA programme targeting workers with a migrant background and initiatives under the Coalition Women in Tech. The **European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)** complements ESF+ by co-financing regional digital infrastructure, innovation capacity and SME digitalisation, with particular relevance to the five Smart Industry EDIHs operating across Dutch provinces.

The **Recovery and Resilience Plan (RRP)** allocated approximately **€1.2 billion (26% of total RRP funding)** to digital priorities, covering investments in quantum computing, artificial intelligence, the digitalisation of education, and smart mobility infrastructure. The six EDIHs are additionally co-funded through the **Digital Europe Programme** at €1.8 million per hub per year (EU 40%, national government 40%, regional authority 20%), ensuring seven-year operational continuity. Collectively, these instruments — ESF+, ERDF, RRP, and Digital Europe — provide a layered financial architecture that connects European strategic priorities with national and regional implementation, while conditioning access through administrative and co-financing requirements that shape which actors are best positioned to benefit.

Figure 3 Governance model ; Source: open.overheid.nl

2.3 Policy Monitoring & Evaluation

The **Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs** is accompanied by a structured monitoring and evaluation framework. The framework combines high-level trend tracking through a dedicated **national monitor, parliamentary accountability through periodic progress reporting, and multi-level governance coordination** to reduce fragmentation across national, regional and sectoral actors. The Action Plan is explicitly designed as a dynamic policy instrument, subject to **ongoing adjustment based on monitoring outcomes and evaluation evidence**. This adaptive orientation is central to its logic: rather than fixing a rigid programme of measures at the outset, the **Action Plan commits to reviewing its effectiveness** and revising its content as data and feedback accumulate. Responsibility for monitoring is shared across three ministries — the Ministry of Economic Affairs (EZK, lead), the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (OCW), and the Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment (SZW). EZK chairs the inter-ministerial steering function, while PTvT (Platform Talent voor Technologie) provides the operational and regional coordination backbone.

The **“Monitor for the Action Plan on Green and Digital Jobs”** launched in April 2025, constituting the primary instrument for tracking structural trends in STEM education and the technology labour market. It is publicly accessible at “agdb.nl/monitor” and updated annually at pillar level, with selected indicators refreshed more frequently where data availability permits. The Monitor is intentionally high-level in scope. It tracks structural trends rather than the outputs of individual programmes, and links to more granular data sources for sectoral and regional analysis, including a. **Dashboard Education–Labour Market Technology (PTvT) — detailed data on education-to-labour-market flows in technology**, b. **Pre-edict — ICT labour-market data**, c. **CBS StatLine — national labour-market and education statistics** and d. **Business Policy in Focus — policy-instrument tracking and evaluation**

The data generated by the Monitor is intended to serve policymakers and delivery organisations at national, regional and sectoral levels, providing shared evidence base for planning and coordination decisions. The Monitor is structured around **three of the Action**

Plan's four pillars. Pillar 4 (governance and coordination) is addressed through the governance architecture described rather than through quantitative indicators.

Pillar 1 monitors choice behaviour among young people — the primary pipeline into the technology workforce. The Monitor tracks key decision points in the education system, with breakdowns by gender and background. Key indicators and current findings: The share of pupils opting for a technology or science profile remains broadly stable: approximately 20% in Secondary Vocational Education (VMBO), 36% in Higher General Continued Education (HAVO) and 60% in Preparatory Scientific Education (VWO) for the 2024/25 cohort.:

Figure 4 Profile choice in secondary education; Source: Monitor for the A.G.D.B

A pronounced gender gap persists, particularly in VMBO, where 34% of boys choose a technical profile compared to only 6% of girls. At VWO level the gap narrows substantially (62% vs. 58%).

Figure 5 Gender and background breakdown; Source: Monitor for the A.G.D.B

Pillar 2 - Inflow and retention in the technology labour market monitors personnel developments in technical and ICT occupations, the evolution of vacancy pressures, and the mobility behaviour of the existing workforce. Key indicators and current findings shows that since 2014, the number of people employed in technology occupations has grown by 26%,

compared to 17% of the total working population, and the number of electrical engineers, software and application developers, and natural scientists has more than doubled. Women represent 16.6% of technology workers in 2024, up from 12.6% in 2013.

Moreover, in 2024, 689,000 people hold a digital occupation, representing 7% of the total working population. Gender composition remains heavily skewed: 82% male, 18% female. Unemployment among technically trained workers stood at 2.8% in 2024, compared to a national average of 3.7%, reflecting persistently tight labour market conditions. Technically trained workers earn a consistently higher hourly wage than the national average, supporting retention. In Q4 of 2024, 75,600 vacancies remained open in technology occupations and 22,700 in digital jobs — a slight decline from the 2022 peak but still far above pre-2016 levels (29,200 and 13,300 respectively). Technical and digital professionals exhibit below-average occupational and employer switching rates. When job changes do occur, workers largely remain within their own occupational class, suggesting strong occupational identity and limited cross-sector spillover.

Pillar 3 monitors trends in labour productivity and business innovation, with particular attention to technology-intensive sectors and the digitalisation of the Dutch economy. Key indicators and current findings: The Netherlands ranks in the global top ten for labour productivity. After strong growth between 1996 and 2000 driven by ICT adoption, productivity growth slowed after 2008 and has declined in recent years, partly attributable to the scaling down of natural gas production and lower productivity among self-employed workers. Between 2014 and 2023, productivity growth was strongest in construction (2.1%), industry (2.0%) and information and communication (1.5%). The energy sector has seen a decline since 2022.

Long-run trends in the economic contribution of technology-intensive industries are tracked to contextualise workforce and skills demand. Survey-based evidence on how employers experience and assess productivity developments in their sectors. R&D expenditure and innovation activity rates across firm sizes and sectors. The share of firms actively deploying digital tools and technologies, disaggregated by industry. Uptake of AI, cloud computing and automation tools, tracked at sector level to identify leaders and laggards in the digital transition.

Beyond the technical Monitor, the **Action Plan** is subject to **periodic parliamentary accountability through formal progress letters addressed to the lower house of Parliament**. The 2025 report presented the following headline findings alongside the formal launch of the Monitor: a. 75,600 technology vacancies and 22,700 digital vacancies remained open in Q4 2024, b. Enrolment trends in STEM education showed modest positive movement at MBO level but continued demographic pressure at higher levels, c. The governance structure for Pillar 4 was operationalised, including the establishment of a national course consultation and the appointment of regional facilitators across all Dutch provinces.

The evidence gathered through the Monitor and the 2025 progress report confirms that the challenge remains acute. Nearly **100,000 technology and digital vacancies remain open**, the gender gap in technical education and employment persists at all but at the highest academic levels, and aggregate labour productivity has declined in recent years despite continued investment in digitalisation.

2.4 Synergies with other EU initiatives

The digital transition process in the Netherlands creates concrete synergies with a range of broader EU policy domains and funding programmes. These linkages are not merely strategic alignments but translate into tangible financial and operational support. The **Horizon Europe** programme (€95.5 billion, 2021–2027) supports skills-related research through projects such as Skills2Capabilities, SkillResilience4EU and SKILLAIbility. **Erasmus+** (€26.2 billion, 2021–2027) contributes through Cooperation Partnerships, Centres of Vocational Excellence (CoVEs) and Teacher Academies that strengthen STEM and digital education pathways. **InvestEU** (€26.2 billion in EU guarantees) provides scale-up finance for technology adoption and productivity, directly relevant to SME digitalisation under Pillar 3. The **LIFE Programme** (€5.4 billion, 2021–2027) supports capacity-building and governance projects aligned with the energy and digital transition, including LIFE21-CET-BUILDSKILLS-BUS-NL and LIFE23-CET-Skills4DHC. The following table summarises the main links between these EU initiatives and the Action Plan’s pillars.

Table 3 Synergies of Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs with other EU initiatives

Policy domain	Links	Examples
Regional domain	EU instruments reinforce place-based solutions, regional capacity building, and policy learning for skills, inclusion, and digital public services.	INTERREG, URBACT, European Urban Initiative (EUI)
	Supports school–business collaboration, labour-market transitions, and mobility schemes that enhance employability through skills development, guidance, and transnational work experience	EURES, ALMA, Youth Employment Support
Economic domain	Strengthens cooperation in digital and green education, vocational excellence, teacher training, and inclusion strategies for disadvantaged learners.	Erasmus+ (Cooperation Partnerships, CoVEs, Teacher Academies)
	Provides scale-up finance, innovation support, and market-building instruments for technology adoption and productivity.	InvestEU, Single Market Programme (SMP), IPCEIs (hydrogen, microelectronics), EIT Digital
	Horizon Europe projects complement national and regional measures on digital literacy, STEM training, labour-market transitions, and SME digitalisation.	Skills2Capabilities, GS4S – Global Strategy for Skills, Migration and Development, Link4Skills, SkillResilience4EU, SKILLAIbility, Skills4EOSC

Policy domain	Links	Examples
Environmental domain	Supports coordination, capacity building, and governance projects aligned with the Action Plan's pillars, particularly in energy transition and digital-enabled sustainability.	LIFE Programme (LIFE23-CET-HeatCraftHP, LIFE21-CET-BUILDSKILLS-BUS-NL, LIFE23-CET-Skills4DHC)
	Helps cities and regions implement circular systemic solutions across sectors and value chains, often requiring digital capabilities for data, monitoring, and traceability.	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI)
Social domain	Provides access to skills intelligence, good practices, and funding guidance, supporting implementation capacity without duplicating national structures.	Pact for Skills
	Promotes apprentice mobility and offers practical resources to strengthen STEM/ICT apprenticeship pathways, including cross-border learning.	European Alliance for Apprenticeships

3 Policy analysis from the inequalities perspective

The **Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs** was designed primarily as a supply-side intervention to address structural labour shortages in technical and digital occupations. While its four-pillar architecture represents a structurally coherent policy response, the plan's effectiveness depends not only on expanding the talent pipeline but also on ensuring equitable access to digital opportunities across social groups, regions, and employment contexts. A critical examination of the assumptions embedded in the plan's design reveals how inequality risks arise across different stages of the policy cycle and why, despite its formal inclusivity, the Action Plan may produce structurally selective outcomes.

The **most consequential assumption** concerns the adequacy of network governance. The Action Plan proceeds on the basis that coordination without formal hierarchical authority, relying on the convening power of the three lead ministries and the sector-level credibility of the Sector Action Plans, is sufficient to overcome the fragmentation that has historically characterised Dutch technical workforce policy. **While this model offers flexibility and preserves regional autonomy, it carries a structural risk** that is particularly acute in the Dutch context: where institutional capacity is uneven — as it is between large firms and SMEs, or between metropolitan and peripheral regions — network governance tends to reproduce rather than correct existing asymmetries. The assumption that coordination alone can substitute for redistributive authority therefore constitutes the foundational limitation of the plan's design.

The plan also assumes that **increasing educational inflow**, improving retention, and stimulating lateral entry will be sufficient — yet this orientation does not adequately account for several compounding structural factors. The contraction of international skilled migration, which fell by 39% between 2022 and 2024 following the abolition of the 30% tax ruling and the tightening of eligibility criteria, has significantly reduced a key source of technical talent without any compensatory mechanism within the Action Plan. At the same time, structural barriers continue to limit participation by women, workers with a migration background, and individuals in non-standard employment. Without targeted demand-side measures and inclusion instruments, supply-side expansion risks reproducing the demographic profile of the existing workforce rather than diversifying it.

This supply-side orientation is further compounded by the assumption, embedded in Pillar 3, that accelerating technological and process innovation in firms can compensate for demographic constraints on labour supply. While productivity-enhancing investment can reduce labour intensity, the evidence indicates that SMEs — which account for approximately 65% of Dutch employment — **face structural barriers to technology adoption** that public support programmes have not fully resolved, including limited financial resources, higher opportunity costs, and lower absorptive capacity. The 2025 Digital Decade Country Report identifies smaller Dutch enterprises as persistently lagging in the adoption of AI and data analytics, and the OECD records a skill mismatch rate of 37%, above the EU average of 35%, as a binding constraint on labour mobility. Productivity gains are therefore unlikely to substitute for workforce expansion at the scale required by the 2030 national targets.

The spatial dimension of these assumptions is equally significant. The governance model assumes that PTVT provincial account holders and the Regional Action Plans developed by all Dutch provinces in 2024 are sufficient to ensure an equitable territorial distribution of digital transition opportunities. The evidence does not support this. Digital employment remains heavily concentrated in Amsterdam, Rotterdam, The Hague, Utrecht, and Eindhoven, and **OECD (2024) analysis shows that urban workers are 11.2 percentage points more likely to be employed in occupations exposed to generative AI**, and 1.4 times more exposed overall. Employment rates ranged from 79.1% in Limburg to 84.1% in North Brabant in 2023, yet the Action Plan contains no territorial equity objective, no instruments for directing additional resources to regions most exposed to transition-related disruption, and no dedicated investment envelopes for peripheral provinces. In the absence of redistributive instruments, regional coordination reproduces spatial inequality rather than correcting it.

Finally, and perhaps most directly relevant to the plan's stated equity ambitions, is the assumption that its suite of lifelong learning initiatives will be accessible to the full range of workers requiring reskilling. The prevailing **lifelong learning paradigm frames skills development primarily as an individual responsibility**, which structurally advantages workers with stable employment, financial security, and supportive employers, while placing the highest adaptive burden on those least equipped to bear it. Citizens from outside the EU face an unemployment rate of 10.8% against a national average of 3.6%, and women with a migration background record an employment rate of just 54%, compared with 69% for all women. Simultaneously, Monitor AGDB data (2025) reveal significant untapped potential: at VWO level, students with Turkish or Indonesian backgrounds choose science profiles at a rate of 67%, compared with 58% among students with two Dutch-born parents — a disparity that remains unaddressed by any targeted support mechanism within the Action Plan. **The plan includes no provisions for credential recognition, no language-integrated vocational training, no ethnic diversity targets for technical professions, and no mechanism to reconcile domestic supply ambitions with the contraction of international skilled migration.**

Taken together, these assumptions reveal a policy framework that is formally inclusive but structurally selective. **Between 2022 and 2030, an estimated 150,000 jobs in basic and intermediate skill segments are projected to disappear, while 400,000 new positions will be created in advanced skill segments.** Without inclusion mechanisms targeted at the groups most exposed to displacement — low-skilled workers, women, migrants, and residents of peripheral regions — the Action Plan risks concentrating its benefits among those already best positioned to benefit, thereby deepening rather than narrowing the structural inequalities it implicitly seeks to address.

Findings from the interviews conducted for this study reveal that the Netherlands' digital transition is shaped by a combination of institutional fragmentation and persistent skills shortages. Despite the country's strong technological base, interviewees consistently described a governance landscape in which responsibilities are divided between ministries oriented toward innovation and competitiveness and those focused on inclusion, education, and public values. This institutional bifurcation contributes to fluctuating strategic priorities and undermines the coherence of national digital policy. Although the Netherlands performs strongly in digital infrastructure and innovation ecosystems, long-standing structural

constraints in STEM education and the domestic supply of ICT graduates continue to impede progress.

Interviewees also emphasised that labour market shortages should not be interpreted as evidence of declining ICT employment. Rather, they reflect measurement limitations and the rapid expansion of digital sectors that outpaces the adaptive capacity of education and training systems. While the Dutch model of public–private collaboration is well established, tensions persist between employers’ short-term demand for specialised technical skills and the long-term investment required to build broad foundational digital competencies. Overall, the interviews portray a system with considerable strengths but also institutional and educational constraints that limit both the pace and inclusiveness of the digital transition.

3.1 Drivers of inequalities in digital transition policy

Table 4 Drivers of inequalities

Drivers	Subcategory	Definition
Institutional capacities	Fragmented governance, lack of redistributive tools, demand-driven training, strong PPP model	Fragmented governance, the absence of redistributive tools, weak inclusion mechanisms, a demand-driven training model, and a strong but insufficient public–private partnerships system
Economic dynamics	Skills shortages, part-time trap, decline in skilled, metropolitan concentration	Skills shortages, the part-time trap and the metropolitan concentration of digital employment together create an economy where advanced skills are scarce, opportunities cluster in cities and structural inequalities deepen across regions and social groups.
Societal change	Gender gaps, migration-related exclusion, unequal training access, urban–rural divides, untapped migrant-background talent	Gender gaps, migration-related exclusion, unequal access to training, urban–rural divides and the persistent underuse of migrant-background talent together create a societal landscape in which women, people with a migration background, precariously employed workers and residents of peripheral regions face structural barriers to education, skills development and labour-market progression, reinforcing unequal participation in the Dutch green and digital transitions.
Technology developments	Rapid digital expansion, AI exposure gap, rising demand for advanced skills	Rapid AI adoption and automation create demand for advanced skills and organisational transformation. Policy attention remains stronger on technological development than on structured career pathways and workforce

Drivers	Subcategory	Definition
		transition mechanisms, risking polarisation between high-skilled and routine workers.
Regulatory framework	Skilled-migration restrictions, no territorial equity, EU-level policy pressures	Skilled-migration restrictions, the absence of just-transition provisions, the lack of a territorial equity objective and growing EU-level policy pressures together create a regulatory environment that limits access to international talent, leaves workers in carbon-intensive sectors without adequate protection

The Dutch digital transition is shaped by a deeply interdependent configuration of **institutional capacities, economic dynamics, societal change, technological developments and the regulatory framework**, which together constitute a multilayered system of opportunity structures and constraint mechanisms. At the institutional level, persistent deficits—such as **fragmented governance**, the absence of redistributive tools, weak inclusion provisions and a structurally embedded demand-driven training architecture—limit the state’s capacity to steer transitions in an equitable manner. These governance shortcomings undermine strategic coherence, reduce the system’s ability to correct cumulative disadvantage and constrain the effectiveness of even a strong PPP model, which, despite its strengths in innovation coordination, cannot compensate for systemic gaps in institutional design and policy integration.

These institutional constraints intersect with a set of **economic dynamics** that further entrench inequality. Skills shortages, the part-time trap and the metropolitan concentration of high-value digital employment collectively generate a labour-market structure in which advanced skills are both scarce and unevenly distributed. The erosion of middle-skill occupations, combined with the spatial clustering of digital opportunities in major urban hubs, reinforces regional disparities and intensifies competition for talent. These pressures are amplified by the dual structure of the Dutch economy: large firms in high-tech clusters possess the absorptive capacity to invest in digital transformation and workforce development, whereas SMEs face structural constraints—limited redundancy, tighter margins and higher opportunity costs—that systematically reduce their ability to participate in upskilling initiatives, even when public support is available.

Gender gaps, migration-related exclusion, unequal training access, urban–rural divides and the underutilisation of migrant-background talent reflect long-standing patterns of stratification that shape individuals’ capacity to engage with the digital transition. Early educational tracking, differential access to labour-market opportunities and uneven participation in lifelong learning reinforce cumulative disadvantage. Moreover, the prevailing lifelong-learning paradigm—framed primarily as an individual responsibility rather than a collective societal norm—tends to privilege those with stable employment, financial security and supportive employers, while vulnerable adults often require more intensive, personalised and sustained forms of support.

These institutional, economic and societal dynamics are further intensified by rapid **technological developments**. Accelerated digital expansion, widening AI exposure gaps and rising demand for advanced skills create a technological environment that evolves faster than labour-market and governance systems can adapt. In the absence of robust career-transition infrastructures and anticipatory workforce planning, these technological shifts risk deepening labour-market stratification and reinforcing existing inequalities.

Finally, these dynamics unfold within a **regulatory framework** characterised by skilled-migration diversified, unequal opportunities, the absence of just-transition provisions, the lack of a territorial-equity objective and increasing EU-level policy pressures. Compliance-heavy regulatory regimes—such as GDPR, NIS2 and the AI Act—disproportionately burden SMEs and smaller public institutions, which lack the legal and technical capacity to absorb complex governance requirements. Funding mechanisms that favour administratively mature organisations further entrench advantages for established actors. At the same time, restrictive migration policies limit access to international talent, while the absence of territorial-equity instruments reduces the state’s ability to counteract spatial concentration dynamics.

3.2 From policy design to uneven impacts

This section presents the summary of the Netherlands’ digital transition strategy. The summary below presents an overview of factors linking policy priorities, financial resources, governance structures and institutional capacities to expected economic and social outcomes. It highlights how inequality risks may arise across different stages of the policy cycle—from strategic design and funding allocation to implementation, monitoring and long-term evaluation.

The visualisation offers a structured framework for identifying leverage points where policy refinement may be necessary. It clarifies how competitiveness-driven and formally “inclusive” digital policies can nonetheless produce differentiated impacts across firms, workers and social groups. Furthermore, it enables the identification of structural bottlenecks, coordination gaps and unintended distributive effects that shape the Dutch digital transition. In doing so, it provides analytical grounding for assessing whether digital transformation in the Netherlands is evolving in a socially balanced and territorially cohesive manner.

Figure 6 Summary table on Netherland's digital transition

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101132559.

4 Conclusions

The Netherlands has made substantial progress in constructing a comprehensive and ambitious framework for digital transition, combining digital skills development, enterprise digitalisation, and the modernisation of public administration in close alignment with the EU Digital Decade objectives. National initiatives such as the Action Plan for Green and Digital Jobs and the forthcoming Netherlands Digitalisation Strategy demonstrate a strong commitment to technological leadership in areas such as artificial intelligence, semiconductors, quantum technologies and secure digital government.

These policies have delivered tangible results. The Netherlands exceeds EU averages in digital skills attainment and ICT employment, and enterprises show comparatively high levels of digital adoption. Investments in reskilling and upskilling have strengthened labour-market participation and supported productivity growth, while public–private partnerships have fostered collaboration between education providers, industry and government. Moreover, the country’s proactive stance on online safety, disinformation and digital rights reflects an effort to ensure that technological progress is accompanied by strong public-value safeguards.

These inequalities are not accidental side effects but are rooted in structural characteristics of the Dutch economy and governance model. Persistent ICT labour shortages, a constrained graduate pipeline, demographic ageing and political sensitivities around knowledge migration create bottlenecks in talent supply. Network-based governance, while flexible, can generate coordination challenges and uneven institutional capacity across actors. Large firms and established innovation hubs are better positioned to absorb funding, comply with regulatory requirements and invest in advanced technologies, whereas SMEs, vulnerable workers, women in ICT, low-literate adults and migrant populations face comparatively higher adjustment costs and barriers to participation.

From a just transition perspective, the Dutch experience highlights the need to complement competitiveness-driven digital strategies with stronger distributive, inclusion-oriented and place-sensitive instruments. This includes reinforcing early digital literacy in education, expanding and diversifying the ICT graduate pipeline, simplifying funding access for SMEs, embedding wraparound support in reskilling programmes, and strengthening coordination and budget transparency across governance levels. Continuous and impact-oriented monitoring systems are essential to ensure that progress in digital innovation is matched by progress in social cohesion.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process: The authors have used the AI language model developed by OpenAI to help improve the grammar and refine the language of the report. The authors declare that their use of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies is fully compliant with the 'Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research' (European Commission, April 2025).

